

Quantum Oscillator, Translation and Constant Energy Gaps

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The ground state wavefunction of the quantum oscillator is $W_0 = C \exp(-bx^2)$ and the first excited state is $W_1 = axW_0$ where a , C and b are constants. Geometrically, W_0 is a Gaussian centered at $x=0$ and xW_0 creates an orthogonal function to W_0 in a simple manner by splitting a symmetric hump into two humps one positive, one negative. Now $x = (dW_0/dx / W_0)$ so $W_1 = dW_0/dx$, but d/dx is the translation generator i.e. $W_0(x+dx) = W_0(x) + dx dW_0/dx$. Thus not only is W_0 a solution of the quantum oscillator, but its shifted change is also a solution i.e. the first excited state $W_1 = dW_0/dx$. Classically translating a mass at 0 in an oscillator leads to a periodic solution.

The fact that $x = (dW_0/dx/W_0)$, i.e. is a finite polynomial, has important consequences on the energy gaps of an oscillator being constant. Using $W_n(x) = W_0(x)F_n(x)$ where W_n and W_0 are the n th and 0 level wavefunctions in the time independent Schrodinger equation yields:
 $-2mD(n) = d/dx dF_n/dx / F_n + 2 \{dW_0/dx/W_0\} \{dF_n/dx / F_n\}$ ((1)) where $E_n = E_0 + D(n)$. Given that $dW_0/dx / W_0 = Cx$ and noting that $W_1 = xW_0$ i.e. a finite polynomial multiplies W_0 one may consider F_n as a finite polynomial with a leading term of ax^n (to the power of n). Thus ((1)) implies that for the leading x term in any $F_n(x)$: $2mD = 4bn$ where $D(n)$ is the energy gap between the n and $n+1$ levels and $b = .5\sqrt{km}$ where k is the oscillator constant and m the mass. Thus each level is equally spaced in energy.

Thus it seems that behaviour of the oscillator ground state under translations leads to constant energy gaps. For example such behaviour does not occur for $F_n(x)$ which is an infinite power series of x such as $\sin(px)$ which is a solution of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls.

Oscillator Ground State and Orthogonality

A ground state solution may be found by inspection for the quantum oscillator from the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$-1/2m d/dx dW_n/dx + .5kx^2 W_n = E_n W_n(x) \quad ((2))$$

A solution of $C \exp(-.5\sqrt{km}x^2)$ ((3)) is immediately seen. Graphically this is a Gaussian centered at $x=0$ i.e. a single symmetric hump.

It is known mathematically that ((2)) has orthogonal solutions with discrete E_n values. We argue that physically quantum solutions must maintain the identity or information of a state, but wavefunctions are nonlocal. Thus $\int W^*(n_1)(x) W(n)(x) dx = \delta(n_1, n)$. This idea already follows from the free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ which indicates that a given precise p is associated with nonlocality i.e. a wavelength in space. Nevertheless it must maintain its identity or information in space so: $\int dx \exp(-i p_1 x) \exp(ipx) = \delta(p_1, p)$.

Given the idea of orthogonality the first excited state $W_1(x)$ has the property: $\int dx W^*_0(x) W_1(x) = 0$. A positive Gaussian hump which is symmetric about the origin may be multiplied by a function which makes the right side positive and creates a hump because x must

be 0 at the origin to allow for a transition from positive to negative and the same hump, but negative on the left hand side. This is a graphical approach and the function x is the simplest way to accomplish this i.e. one may consider $W_1(x) = xW_0(x)$ as a solution. (In fact one may show that this is a solution of ((2))).

A main point we wish to stress is that:

$$W_1 = xW_0(x) = (dW_0/dx / W_0) W_0 = dW_0/dx \quad ((3))$$

d/dx , however, is the translation generator. $W_0(x)$ describes zero point energy. This is like a mass sitting at zero in the classical world except that in the quantum world there is some motion. Classically one would displace the mass against the spring force and oscillatory motion would ensue. We suggest taking $W_0(x)$ and writing:

$$W_0(x+dx) = W_0(x) + dx dW_0/dx \quad ((4))$$

The shifted piece $dW_0/dx = C x W_0(x)$ is $W_1(x)$ i.e the first excited state of the oscillator.

We point out that x is a finite polynomial. This is important because many functions, such as $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$, are infinite polynomials.

Constant Energy Gap

One may write the solution of ((2)) in the form: $W_n(x) = W_0(x)F_n(x)$ ((5))

Given that $F_1(x) = ax$ we suggest that all $F_n(x)$ must be finite polynomials. This we argue is an important point. Then using ((5)) in ((2)) yields:

$$2mD(n) F_n(x) = -d/dx dF_n/dx - 2 \{dF_n/dx\} \{ dW_0/dx/W_0 \} \quad ((6))$$

where $E_n = E_0 + D(n)$.

$dW_0/dx/W_0 = -2bx$ where $b = .5\sqrt{k/m}$ and $F_n(x)$ is a finite polynomial so one may consider its leading term: ax^n . Thus for any n :

$$2mD(n) a = 2\sqrt{k/m} n a \quad \text{or:} \quad D(n) = \sqrt{k/m} n \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Thus } E_n = \sqrt{k/m} n + E_0 = \sqrt{k/m} (n+.5) \quad ((8))$$

As a result of $F_n(x)$ being a finite polynomial and the simplicity of $dW_0/dx / W_0 = Cx$ ((9)) one quickly sees that energy gaps for a quantum oscillator are constant.

It is interesting, but perhaps not too surprising, that ((9)) holds because for any $V(x)$:

$$-1/2m \{d/dx dW_n/dx / W_n\} = E_n - V(x) \quad ((10))$$

((9)) immediately leads to $d/dx dW_0/dx / W_0$ having a C_1+C_2x form which matches $E_n-V(x)$ for an oscillator. $dW_0/dx / W_0$ is by definition proportional to the average complex momentum in the system and the fact that it is equal to x seems to show that x and p are on the same footing. This is interesting because $\langle p^2 \rangle$ and $\langle x^2 \rangle$ are also on the same footing. This suggests that $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle x \rangle$ are on the same footing, but not necessarily $\langle p \rangle$ and x .

Issue with Infinite Polynomial Functions

One may note that equal energy gaps do not occur for a particle in a box with infinite walls at $x=0$ and $x=L$. There the ground state wavefunction is:

$$W_0(x)=C \sin(3.14x/L) \text{ and } W_1(x)= C_2 \sin(2*3.14x/L) = 2C_2 W_0(x) \cos(3.14x/L) \quad ((11))$$

$F_1(x) = \cos(3.14x/L)$ which is an infinite polynomial. Thus one cannot apply the analysis of the above section to the highest power of x because it is infinite.

Information Considerations

In a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas one may suggest that information $\ln(Cd(x))$ equals $-V(x)/T$ where T is temperature. This then leads to $Cd(x) = \exp(-V/T)$ where $d(x)$ is density. A similar result holds for the ground state oscillator namely:

$$W_0(x) = (1/C) \exp(-.5\text{sqrt}(k/m) xx) \text{ so: } \ln(CW_0) = - V(x)/E_0 \quad ((11)) \text{ where } E_0=.5 \text{sqrt}(k/m).$$

One may call $\ln(CW_0)$ information. Furthermore the average of information for the ground state oscillator is:

$$\text{Integral } dx W_0(x)W_0(x) \ln(W_0) = \text{Integral } dx W_0W_0 (-.5kxx)/E_0 = -\text{Variance}(x) \text{sqrt}(k/m)$$

Thus for the ground state oscillator average information is up to a multiplicative constant the same as average potential energy which follows immediately from the local information condition ((11)). For an oscillator average kinetic energy is the same as average potential energy. Thus for such a system there are not two different pieces of information, one related to average kinetic energy and the other to average potential.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that one may find the ground state wavefunction $W_0(x)= C \exp(-.5\text{sqrt}(k/m)xx)$ for an oscillator by inspection. Imposing orthogonality with $W_1(x)$ the first excited state geometrically suggests a function which converts a Gaussian centered at 0 into two humps with $W_1(x) = 0$ at $x=0$ with one hump being positive and the other negative, but otherwise symmetric. The simplest way to accomplish this is to multiply $W_0(x)$ by ax where a is a constant. This is in fact the first excited state, but one may note that $dW_0/dx / W_0 = Cx$. Now

d/dx is the generator of translations and classically displacing a mass at $x=0$ leads to oscillations. In the quantum case there is already motion with $W_0(x)$, but one may displace it to obtain the first excited state it seems. This leads to $W_0(x+dx) = W_0(x) + dx dW_0/dx$. Thus: CxW_0 is the first excited state. We stress the importance of x being a finite polynomial.

One may write $W_n(x) = W_0(x) F_n(x)$ with $F_n(x)$ being a finite polynomial, we suggest, because x is a finite polynomial. Inserting into the time-independent Schrodinger equation leads to an equation in $F_n(x)$ on the LHS multiplied by D_n where $E_n = D_n + E_0$ and derivatives of $F_n(x)$ with dF_n/dx multiplied by $(dW_0/dx)/W_0$ or Cx on the RHS. Thus for a finite polynomial one has $C_1 D_n a$ for the leading x power coefficient on the LHS and $C_n a$ on the right handside. Thus D_n is proportional to n and all energy gaps are the same for the oscillator. We note that such an approach does not hold if $F_n(x)$ has an infinite polynomial representation as in the case of a particle in a box with infinite walls. We also note that density information in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas may be linked to $V(x)/T$ in a very similar way that $\ln(W_0(x))$ may be linked to $V(x)/E_0$. Thus there are similarities in information for the ground state oscillator and the spatial density in a MB gas. One may note that usually $W_0(x)$ contains information about average kinetic energy and also average potential energy. In the case of the oscillator these two averages integrated over dx are the same.